

COMPRESSIVE PROPERTY OF GEOPOLYMER BASED SYNTACTIC FOAMS

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ABSTRACT

Syntactic foams were developed in the early 60's and are widely applied to aerospace and submarine industry now. It is a special kind of composite materials which can be synthesized in a mechanical way by mixing hollow particles (the filler) with a resin system (the binder). Geopolymers are amorphous binder materials with three-dimensional structure resulting from the polymerization of aluminosilicate monomers in an alkaline solution. The composition of the final geopolymers can be altered by various factors, such as $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio, concentration of alkaline solution, water content etc. In this work, an alkali aluminosilicates binder, known as geopolymer, was first used as the matrix of syntactic foams. It was prepared from metakaolin, as aluminosilicatic raw powder, and alkaline solution. Three types of hollow microspheres, Ex-lites (ceramic), K1 (glass) and BJO-0930 (phenolic) were used as the fillers. The effect of each type of sphere on the compressive property of the syntactic foam was studied. The addition of Ex-lites and K1 microspheres not only created the interfacial bonding between the microspheres and the matrix, but also altered the molar ratio of Al:Si due to the chemical interaction between spheres and alkaline solution. The volume fraction and chemical compositions of the microspheres also play the important roles in the compressive property of the syntactic foams.

1 INTRODUCTION

Geopolymers, firstly named by Davidovits in 1972 [1], belong to a new class of inorganic polymers formed by combining alkali materials and aluminosilicates. These materials can be a candidate to provide comparable performance to traditional cementitious binders, in a range of applications, but with added advantage of significantly reduced greenhouse emissions [2]. Depending on the raw material selection and processing conditions, geopolymers can exhibit a wide variety of properties and characteristics, including high compressive strength [3], low shrinkage [4], fast or slow setting [5], acid resistance [6], fire resistance and low thermal conductivity [7]. The materials with high aluminosilicate content and alkali hydroxide solution are two sources to synthesize geopolymers. The raw aluminosilicate materials could be natural minerals or industrial wastes. Metakaolin (MK), fly-ash and slag are the three main raw materials as source of aluminosilicate. MK is ideally synthesized by dehydroxylation of phase pure kaolin, with a highly disrupted phyllosilicate structure containing silicon and aluminum only. Although most commercial MK contains levels of impurities, primarily muscovite and titanium dioxide, the effect of the impurities is limited by their both low dissolution and the inability of the products of their dissolution to affect the formation mechanism. In contrast, fly ash and slag are industries waste made up of silicon, aluminum and iron oxides as well as significant calcium which increase the complexity of reaction and affect the geopolymerization mechanisms [8]. In addition, the particle size of MK varies to some degree, but is generally smaller than 5 μm , with the intrinsic size of the clay being in the order of 20 nm. Although the dispersion of particles during mixing affects the degree of reaction somewhat, there is little difference in the reaction of MK-based geopolymer with variation in raw material surface area [9]. The fly ash particles are inhomogeneous and comprise glassy as well as crystalline phases. The inhomogeneity of both in broad distribution and elemental and phase composition causes the difficulty in the process of a consistent product. Thus, MK is a preferred precursor due to its high rate of dissolution in the reactant solution, easier control on the Si/Al ratio and the white colour [10].

Syntactic foam is a special type of composite material synthesized by filling a metal, polymer or ceramic matrix with hollow particles. It was developed in the early 60's and it is widely applied to aerospace and submarine industries now. The term "Syntactic" is derived from the Greek word "syntaktikos" meaning to "arrange together" [11]. The term "foam" is used because of the cellular nature of the materials. Most of the reports found in the literature are about epoxy-based syntactic foam [12-16]. Epoxy resins are formed from a long chain molecular structure similar to vinyl ester with reactive sites at either end. According to [17], the ideal binder used in syntactic foams should comply with the following requirements:

- a) Low viscosity to facilitate rapid filling of the mold,
- b) Easily controlled gelation time to prevent lamination of the composite,
- c) Small exothermal effect during curing,
- d) Low curing shrinkage,
- e) Good adhesion and wettability to the filler,
- f) Compatibility with modifiers and fillers, including diluents, plasticizers, dyes, and flame retardants.

The advantages of epoxies as the binder in syntactic foam are its high strength and modulus, low levels of volatiles, excellent adhesion, low shrinkage, and good chemical resistance, and ease of processing. Depending on the different applications, different types of matrix materials were also studied. For example, phenolic and bismaleimide resin were used to fabricate syntactic foams for high temperature applications [18-21]. Compared with thermoset polymers, geopolymers have been shown to exhibit superior mechanical properties and intrinsically fire resistance due to their inorganic framework. In addition, geopolymers possess good adhesion, good chemical resistance, adjustable viscosity and ease of processing, which meet the requirements of the ideal binder used in syntactic foams [17]. Hence, geopolymer emerges as a candidate to fabricate syntactic foams. In this work, novel MK based syntactic foams containing various types of hollow microspheres were fabricated. Compression study was carried out on the syntactic foams. The effect of the use of different types of hollow microspheres will be discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Raw materials

Three types of hollow microspheres were used as the fillers in this work. The physical properties of different microspheres are listed in Table 1. Hollow silica microspheres (Ex-lites) were purchased from Sunmicrospheres, China. Hollow phenolic microspheres (BJO-0930) were purchased from Asia Pacific/Eastech. Hollow glass microspheres (K1) were purchased from 3M. MK (Metamax®) was purchased from BASF, USA with a composition listed in Table 2. Sodium hydroxide was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.

Type of microsphere	Density (g/cm ³)	Chemical composition	Mean diameter (μm)	Static pressure (MPa)
Ex-lites	0.65	Silica	100.2	17.2
BJO-0930	0.25	Phenolic	71.5	3.4
K1	0.125	Glass	65.0	1.7

Table 1. Physical properties of different types of hollow microspheres.

Component	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃
wt%	53.0	43.8	0.23	0.19	1.70	0.43	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03

Table 2. Chemical composition of MK.

2.2 Preparation of geopolymer based syntactic foams

10, 30 and 50 vol% of the hollow microspheres were calculated and premixed with MK powder. The mixture was shaken using Vortex mixer for 10 mins. 8M of sodium hydroxide was then added to the mixture with slowly stirring to form the slurry. After that, the slurry was poured into a Teflon mold to cure at 40 °C for 2 h, followed by 60 °C for 24 h.

2.3 Mechanical tests

Compression tests were performed in this work. The specimens were machined to blocks of 25.0×25.0×12.0 mm³ according to ASTM Standard C365/C 365M – 05. The tests were carried out at room temperature using an Instron Tester (Model 5567), which has a maximum capacity of 30 KN. The cross-head speed applied was 0.5 mm/min.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

It is noted that there are several factors that affect the compressive strength of syntactic foams [16, 19]. (1) The introduction of air space from the inside of the hollow microspheres. The air space acting as the voids, takes up large volume of the matrix, which in turn reduces the compressive strength. (2) The interfacial bonding between the matrix and the outer surfaces of the hollow microspheres. The compressive strength improves as long as adequate bonding is maintained. (3) Chemical composition of the microspheres. The comparison of compressive strength as a function of hollow microspheres content is shown in Figure 1. It can be seen that the compressive strength of the syntactic foam decreases with increasing filler content. The decrease trend indicates that the hollow space volume increase in the matrix when the hollow microspheres content increases, resulting in the decrease in the compressive strength of the syntactic foam.

As shown in Figure 1, the compressive strength of the syntactic foam containing Ex-lites microspheres is higher than that of the neat geopolymer. The increase trend may be attributed to some combined reasons. The mechanical properties of geopolymers are highly depended on Si/Al ratio [22,

23]. The Ex-lites microspheres consist of high content of SiO_2 . When the microspheres react with NaOH solution during geopolymerization, the dissolution, diffusion or transportation of dissolved Si complexes from the microspheres surface occur. A gel phase is formed resulting from the polymerization between the Si complexes from microspheres and the Si and Al complexes from the MK powders and finally hardening of the gel phase. Due to the chemical reaction between the microspheres and the matrix, the adequate bonding is created. These bonded interfaces will need to be overcome before the crushing of the microspheres and the occurrence of severe damage, which in turn improves the compressive strength [19]. In addition, the Si/Al ratio may be changed in the matrix due to the diffusion and transportation of complexes from microspheres. Normally, the geopolymers with high mechanical properties contain high Si/Al ratio. Therefore, although the Ex-lites microspheres content increases, the compressive strength of the syntactic foam is higher than that of the neat geopolymer. It is worth noting that the evidences, such as EDX, SEM and mapping were not presented here, but will be provided in our future paper.

It can also be seen that K1 microspheres performs inferior compared with Ex-lites microspheres. The compressive strength of the syntactic foam containing K1 microspheres is lower than that of neat geopolymer. The performance of K1 microspheres is also attributed to the formation of the interfacial bonding. The chemical composition of K1 microspheres is soda lime borosilicate. The geopolymerization occurred resulting from the polymerization between Si complexes from K1 microspheres and the Si and Al complexes from MK powders. The adequate interface bonding creates and the Si/Al ratio in the matrix changes, as a resulting of the increase in the compressive strength of the syntactic foam. However, compared with Ex-lites microspheres, the decrease trend for K1 microspheres is observed. The difference between the Ex-lite and K1 microspheres explains that apart from interfacial bonding and Si/Al ratio in the matrix, the material composition of the microspheres is of equal importance for the compressive strength of the syntactic foam. K1 microspheres possess relatively low static pressure. The difference in the static pressure is believed to be an important factor to the difference in the trends of the Ex-lite and K1 microspheres.

Figure 1 also shows the compressive strength of the syntactic foam containing different volume fraction of BJO-0930 microspheres. It is noted that in this work, 50 vol% of BJO-0930 microspheres is not presented because the microspheres cannot be fully wetted by the matrix. Compared with neat geopolymer, the compressive strength of the syntactic foam containing BJO-0930 microspheres is quite low. The chemical composition of BJO-0930 is phenolic, which is inert in the alkaline solution. Although the static pressure of BJO-0930 is superior compared with K1 microspheres, the compressive strength of the syntactic foam containing K1 is higher than that of the one containing the same volume fraction of BJO-0930 microspheres. Therefore, it can be concluded that the mechanical properties of geopolymer based syntactic foams can be affected by four factors. (1) Interface between microspheres and matrix. (2) Si/Al ratio in the matrix. (3) Volume fraction of the microspheres added. (4) Chemical compositions of the microspheres. The detailed results accompanied with discussion including tensile, flexural, compressive and toughness properties will be presented in our future paper.

Figure 1. Compressive strength of syntactic foams containing various volume fractions of hollow ceramic microspheres (Ex-lites), hollow glass microspheres (K1) and hollow phenolic microspheres (BJO-0930).

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the compressive strength of MK based syntactic foams containing various types of microspheres was presented. Results showed that the compressive strength decrease with the increase of microspheres content. The microspheres act as voids in the matrix and weaken the structure. The interfacial bonding creates between the matrix and Ex-lite and K1 microsphere with the combination of the change of the Si/Al ratio in the matrix, resulting in the increase in the compressive strength of the syntactic foams. The chemical composition of the microspheres plays an important role in the compressive strength of the syntactic foam. The details mechanisms and evidences will be studied and presented in our future paper. In addition, the density, which is the key factor of the foam materials, will also be presented soon. It is expected that the work for the geopolymer based syntactic foam will open a new door for the applications of geopolymer materials.

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